

Integration of Students' Needs with Career Opportunities and Dual Career Development among Students in Secondary Schools in Sebei Sub-Region

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Abstract: Dual careers have become a relevant matter in the world of work as one of the tools that can improve social life. In that regard, this study sought to examine the influence of integration of students' needs with career opportunities on dual career development among students. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with both qualitative and quantitative approaches in which a population of 360 people involving headteachers, deputy headteachers, Directors of Studies, Career guidance teachers, Games teachers; Sports officers; and students who have been involved in games and sports in the schools were targeted. The study used a sample of 186 people selected using purposive, simple random and cluster sampling techniques. Data was collected using a validated and pre-tested self-administered questionnaire and interview guide. Analysis of the quantitative data collected was done using descriptive and inferential statistics generated by the SPSS; while analysis of the qualitative data was done using thematic and content analysis.

The findings of the study revealed that for integration of students needs with careers and dual career development; $R^2 = .495$, $F=179.242$, $Sig= .000 < .05$ for academic career and $R^2 = .670$, $F=371.676$, $Sig= .000 < .05$ for sports career. The study concluded that integration of students' needs with career had a higher influence for sports than for academic career development. The study finally recommends that career teachers need to provide guidance tailored to the needs of each student to allow for integration of student needs with career opportunities. Mass guidance to groups of students does not provide for integration of individual needs.

Keywords: Integration of Students' Needs, Career Opportunities, Dual Career Development, Students Sebei Sub-Region.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background

Integrating career development into the classroom is a great way to ensure students see the connections between coursework and their future career or continuing education goals (European Union, 2012). students around the world are faced with a variety of life and career options that increasingly demand knowledge and skills. In recent years, educators have placed great importance on the principle that high school should equip students not only with academic knowledge

but also with career-related competencies. Hence, integrating career development, which typically includes the topics of self-exploration, career exploration, and career development, plays a vital role in supporting young people to manage their experiences related to career and preparing them for the future (O'Neil, et al, 2013).

The formation of a dual career, on the other hand, combines both academic and athletic experiences, as well as a job or line of work mixed with participation in sports (Swann, Moran, & Piggott, 2015). The goal of dual career development, as consistently stated in policy statements, is to help students develop the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes necessary to comprehend and succeed both inside and outside of the classroom, supporting both personal and societal economic performance (OECD, 2010). In a nutshell, dual career development is a plan designed to help someone get ready for a variety of professional choices following graduation. Considering numerous employment choices beyond your time in school is a wise decision in the present climate, regardless of your objectives, and it's crucial to start early. A variety of cooperative and partnership activities are essential to the success of professions education programs in schools and colleges.

In the majority of the nations where dual career arrangements have been established for some time, there are occasionally gaps in the strong agreements between the sport system and the educational or professional worlds. They might also be lacking in a stable legal system or political strategy. The development and improvement of sustainable dual career programs that allow for individualized arrangements for exceptional and elite athletes worldwide, whether in their capacity as student-athletes or employee-athletes, could benefit from careers education.

Dual careers are still quite new, even though career education has long been practiced in Uganda. However, it has been noted that Ugandans continue to change careers. It is wise to give studies on dual careers and career education considerable thought. The current state of dual careers and career education in Uganda is discussed in this subsection. The Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) in Uganda has as its vision "*Quality Education and Sports for All,*" and its mission "*To provide for, support, guide, coordinate, regulate, and promote delivery of quality Education and Sports to all persons in Uganda; for national integration, individual, and national development*" (ESSP, 2017). This suggests that Uganda's MoES takes into account the dual career development of all learners, specifically academic and athletic. The ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20 has only designated 32 schools as sports centers, nevertheless. As a result, career education is not typically prioritized in schools for the benefit of students. Therefore, it is still unclear how the learners' development of dual careers was affected by the lack of emphasis placed on careers education.

The Ministry of Education and Sports in Uganda is a dual ministry since, in line with its mission, it aims to help students advance both their academic and athletic abilities. In an ideal world, the educational system would prepare students for careers in both athletics and academia. There is no official training for service providers in Uganda's educational curriculum, despite the fact that career education services were created in the USA more than 100 years ago. The educational programs in Uganda are structured to get students ready for the next level of learning. Prior to 2020, Uganda's secondary education curriculum gave priority to topic knowledge at the expense of helping students develop marketable and transferrable skills and competences (NCDC, 2020). The previous secondary education curriculum was initially created for a select group of exceptional kids headed for careers in the public sector. As a result, every learner will be able to acquire understandings and skills in accordance with his or her capacity, according to NCDC (2020). NCDC (2020) further affirms that the new curriculum will be designed so that it gives every learner the chance to gain the knowledge, skills, and attitudes they need as well as the opportunity to receive proper acknowledgment for accomplishments while they are in school.

Career instructors have been in charge of career education in secondary schools in Uganda up until the introduction of the new lower secondary school curriculum. These educators work to provide knowledge on the following topics and frequently take part in activities that are linked to them, including assessing career needs, creating career chances, fusing student needs with professional opportunities, and routine monitoring (NCDC, 2017). Their level of interaction with the kids differs from one school to the next due to a variety of circumstances, including time constraints, facilitation, and support from other stakeholders, to name a few. The teachers work hard to help the students establish personal development plans that should be founded on their beliefs, aspirations, and self-awareness.

Statement of the Problem

Despite integration of career development into curriculum instruction in secondary schools, dual career development remains a significant obstacle. Due to its mission of offering top-notch sports and education to all students, Uganda's Ministry of Education and Sports supports the conventional dual career growth. In order to help learners transition from

one career to another in the 21st century successfully and without major obstacles, dual career development is the way to go. Secondary schools educate pupils about careers through their careers teachers in this regard. However, a lot of Sebei students have had trouble preparing for both a career in academics and a career in sports. Numerous students are still struggling with the issue of dual career development, and the majority of them are unable to conduct efficient self-evaluations, explore opportunities, identify career opportunities, integrate their goals with employee needs, or conduct routine choice monitoring (OECD, 2018). There are research on sports and athletics (Taras, 2005; Yiannakis and Melnick, 2001), but there is little information on how integration of career development affects the growth of dual careers in Uganda, particularly in the Sebei sub-region. Before students enter the final stages of their education, secondary schools should ensure that there is a balanced progression of their careers. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of integration of career development the curriculum on on dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Purpose

To assess the influence of integration of students' career development on dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Significance of Study

The results of this study may help stakeholders in different ways; for instance: It will assist the Ministry of Education and Sports in making sure that Uganda has the chance to create an advanced secondary level curriculum, which will be essential in shaping young people into become more independent, proactive professionals capable of competing for jobs right out of school, especially if they cannot afford to pursue a more rigorous study at the university level. It will assist the District Education Officers in promoting the National Curriculum Development Centre's (NCDC) curriculum in order to encourage dual career development among Ugandan youth. For better outcomes in both academics and athletics, it will allow school officials to give their kids' dual career development first priority. The findings might serve as a foundation for the academia.

Scope of the Study

The study was done in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region of eastern Uganda, close to the Kenya-Uganda border. The region is located 295 kilometers (183 miles) northeast of Kampala, the capital city of Uganda, along 01 24N, 34 27E. The Sebei sub-region was chosen for this study because it has recently produced the top athletes, both men and women, and because many students there are experimenting with dual career development, particularly in athletics. The study focused on the influence of integrating students' needs with those opportunities on dual career development among secondary school students in the Sebei sub-region. The period from 2015 to 2021 was considered for the study because this was the period that witnessed renewed efforts in career education with challenges in dual career development (Otwine & Oonyu, 2018).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Cosh and Tully (2014); and Rugangila (2019).

Theoretical Review

The study adopted the Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory

Albert Bandura proposed the Social Cognitive Theory in 1986 as an expansion of the prior Social Learning Theory he had created in 1977. According to the idea, learning can be partially attributed to observing others while taking into account social interactions, personal experiences, and outside media influences. According to the hypothesis, when individuals watch a model engage in an action and experience the results, they retain the chronology of events and make use of it to direct future behavior. The Social Cognitive Theory is put out from an agent perspective, which contends that people are self-developing, self-regulating, self-reflective, and proactive rather than just being formed by their environments or inner forces (Pajares, 2009). According to Pajares (2009), human agency primarily takes three forms: individual, proxy, and collective. Individual agency refers to a person's direct influence on the environment, while proxy agency refers to another person's efforts to protect the individual's interests.

The central idea of social cognitive theory, according to Bandura (1988), is that information is acquired or learned by observation of models. The models may come from media sources or interpersonal imitation. Effective modeling offers overarching principles and methods for handling various circumstances. According to the idea, learning is most likely to happen when the observer and the model have a high degree of identification and the observer also has a high level of self-efficacy (Urich, 2017). Self-efficacy is the degree to which a person has confidence in their ability to learn a specific skill. Self-efficacy beliefs influence behavior through intervening motivational, cognitive, and affective processes, making them a significant set of proximal determinants of human motivation, affect, and action (Bandura, 1989).

Mastery experience, a process that aids a person in completing straightforward tasks that pave the way for more difficult goals, can be used to build or develop self-efficacy; Improving physical and emotional states means making sure a person is rested and at ease before attempting a new task. Social modeling offers a recognizable model that illustrates the processes that accomplish a behavior. Less patient and less unhurried people are more likely to fail to engage in desired conduct. Verbal persuasion is motivating someone to finish a job or adopt a particular behavior (McAlister et al., 2008).

Integration of students' needs enables the spectator to experience a 1:1 likeness with the model, which may increase the likelihood that the observer will carry out the modeled behavior (Bandura, 1988). People are more likely to imitate the behaviour of someone they can relate to. The likelihood that the observer learns and imitates the modeled behavior increases with the number of similarities or emotional connections that are seen between them. SCT is frequently used in media studies as it relates to sports, health, education, and other topics. For instance, Hardin and Greer in 2009 researched the gender-typing of sports within the theoretical framework of social cognitive theory and proposed that gender perception of sports among American college students was highly influenced by gender-role socialization and sports media use. Therefore, Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory was appropriate in predicting the results of this study on integration of students' needs and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory

The notion of career development examines ways to enhance professional development, career trajectories, and overall job satisfaction. Understanding professional development theory can be a crucial first step in figuring out your fundamental values, aptitudes, and chosen route. While different career development theories make different claims, all of them stress the value of forming meaningful professional ambitions and cultivating a positive emotional relationship with one's work. The developmental hypothesis was developed by Donald Super on the premise that your self-perception evolves. The way a person values their profession and the goals they set is shaped by time and experience. According to this view, a person's lifetime constitutes their entire "career." Five stages of career growth were identified by Super: Growth, Exploration, Establishment, Maintenance and Decline.

Super believed that how satisfied people were with their careers depended on how they perceived themselves at each of these five stages of development. A work-life balance, for example, may be more important at the maintenance stage than in the establishment stage. Even if a person's career doesn't change, experience and time might change how they perceive their area of work. This study on career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region was successfully supported by Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory, it was found.

2. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Individuals do not, however, undertake their careers in a vacuum, as decisions about future trajectories need to be considered within the context of the broader world (Herr, 2008; King, 2004). Facilitating this decision-making is the process of career management that has been defined as an 'ongoing problem-solving process in which information is gathered, awareness of oneself and the environment is increased, career goals are set, strategies are developed to attain

those goals, and feedback is obtained' (Greenhaus et al., 2009). Career management, therefore, involves 'the analysis, planning and action that can be taken by an individual at any stage of their career – and ideally throughout it – to actively increase the chance of doing well' (Forsyth, 2002).

In essence, success has to be proactively sought and job seekers need to have a clear idea of what they mean by success and how to achieve it. Whilst striving for this career success people face a number of developmental tasks and challenges. If individuals understand these activities, they can formulate strategies that are most appropriate to a particular period in their careers. To support this, organizations attuned to the unfolding pattern of a career over an employee's employment lifespan can design developmental programmes suitable for the different stages of an individual's career (Greenhaus et al., 2009). This emphasizes the interplay between career management and career development, a theme discussed later in the chapter. It also highlights that understanding and conceptualizing careers is a critical task bridging the levels of national policy, organization practice and individual expectations.

Preparation for and engagement in career management and the career development process necessitates an understanding of the contemporary career and its diverse depictions over time. Examining the historical meanings ascribed to the definition of 'career' unearths the shifting sands of emphasis over the past century. There are four distinctive stages of this process. (i) The roots of career development derived from Parsons' (1909) three-step formula for choosing a career that involved the matching of personal requirements with the external environment. (ii) Chicago School of Sociologists, epitomized by Hughes (1958), took an expansive life perspective approach, underscoring the relationship between professional and personal biographies. (iii) At this stage, the concept of career returned to a more restricted occupational and organizational orientation, situating career within the context of stable, employment structures (Wilensky, 1961), typified by linear, upward progression across a limited number of firms with a focus on extrinsic rewards and organizational career management. (iv) This reflects a movement to a more contemporary understanding of career, exemplified by broader, experienced-focused, post-organizational descriptions, attempting to replicate how individuals enact their career in a changing world (Sullivan and Baruch, 2009).

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with both qualitative and quantitative paradigms was used. Kothari (2006) affirms that the main idea behind using this type of design is to better define an opinion, attitude, or behaviour held by a group of people on a given subject. The target population for the study consisted of various categories of people who included members of the headteachers (15) and deputy headteachers (15) of the selected secondary schools, Directors of Studies (15, DOS), career guidance teachers (15), games teachers (30), sports officers (03), students who have been involved in games and sports (267) in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. The total target population of study constituted of 360 people. Basing on the Glenn (1992) sampling table, the sample of the study constituted of 186 respondents who were sampled using purposive and cluster sampling techniques. Table 1.1 presents the summary of population, sample size and sampling techniques used in the study.

Table 1.1: Population, Sample Size and Sampling Techniques used in the Study

Category	Population	Sample Size	Sampling Technique
Sports Officers	03	03	Census
Headteachers	15	08	Purposive
Deputy Headteachers	15	08	Purposive
Directors of Studies	15	08	Purposive
Teachers (CG, Games/Sports)	45	23	Cluster Sampling
Students	267	136	Cluster Sampling
Total	360	186	

Source: District Education Registries for Kapchorwa, Kween and Bukwo (2021)

Data Collection Methods

The study used two methods of data collection, the questionnaire (survey) method and the interview method. The instruments of data collection were the self-administered questionnaires, interview guides and checklists.

Quality Control

Validity of Instruments

According to Hammersley (1987), an instrument is valid or true if it represents accurately those features of the phenomena that it is intended to describe, explain or theorize. Insofar, validity is concerned with two main issues: whether the instruments used for measurement are accurate and whether they are actually measuring what they want to measure (Winter, 2000). Ritchie and Lewis (2003) indicated that the validity of research is conceived as the precision or correctness of the research finding. In this study, validity of the instrument was assessed through consultation with experts and rating the items and then computing the Content Validity Index (CVI) which is a measure of validity of the instrument. From the rating, the researchers computed the Content Validity Index (CVI) and got a value of 0.81 which according to George and Mallery (2003) scale, meant that the validity of the instrument was good and worthy for use in data collection.

Reliability of Instrument

Smith et al., (2008) define reliability as the extent to which data collection techniques or analysis procedures yield consistent findings. Marshall and Rossman (1999); and Seale (1999) argued that the absolute replication of studies is very difficult to achieve since they reflect realities at the time they were collected and in a situation which is likely to change. A good practice of reliability can be enhanced through an aspect of reflexivity, which is showing the audience of research studies as much as possible of the procedures that have led to a particular set of conclusions (Seale, 1999). In this study, the researcher pre-tested the research instrument on a reasonable number of respondents, who were not used in the final data collection process. After pre-testing, the Chronbach's Alpha (α) Coefficient was computed using SPSS (ver. 20). The Chronbach Alpha obtained was 0.894 and according to George and Mallery (2003) scale, this was interpreted as good reliability.

Data Processing and Analysis

Since data and information for each research question were gathered from various sources and using different techniques, it was important to synthesize it or put it together in order to obtain a comprehensive picture of the situation regarding each research question in the study. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to compute descriptive statistics i.e. frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. From the descriptive statistic (means) the inferential statistics i.e. simple linear regression was generated using SPSS. For qualitative data analysis, collected data were transcribed, coded, categorized and themes built through content analysis. This was meant to enhance readability and understanding of the research findings by a larger public interested in issues of career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Uganda.

Ethical Considerations

In terms of ethical considerations, the researcher first had to be cleared by the ethical committee of the university and then obtain an introductory letter to the field. It was also necessary to seek consent from the respondents before questionnaires and interviews were administered. The respondents were also assured of anonymity and confidentiality of all the information provided in the introductory part of the self-administered questionnaire. During interviews, the researcher ensured that items in the interview guide or the questionnaire did not infringe on the personality of the respondents.

4. STUDY FINDINGS

Demographic Data of Respondents

The respondents were required to indicate their sex, age bracket, level of education and marital status. The detailed results about each characteristic are presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Demographic Data of Respondents

Category	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	122	65.9
Female	63	34.1
Total	185	100.0

Age Bracket		
20-29 Years	126	68.1
30-39 Years	23	12.4
40-49 Years	24	13.0
Above 50 Years	12	6.5
Total	185	100.0
Education Level		
Diploma	20	10.8
Degree	30	16.2
Masters	12	6.5
A-level	123	66.5
Total	185	100.0
Responsibility		
Deputy Headteachers	12	6.5
Headteachers	8	4.3
Teachers	42	22.7
Students	123	66.5
Total	185	100.0

Source: Primary data (2022)

Out of the 185 respondents who completed the self-administered questionnaires, there were more male than female respondents. According to Table 4.2, 65.9% of the respondents were male while 34.1% of them were female respondents. This implies that in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, more men than women have been deployed to teach the students. From Table 1.2, majority (68.1%) of the respondents were in the age bracket of 20-29 years old while 12.4% were in the age bracket of 30-39 years old. Another 13.0% of them were in the age bracket of 40-49 years while only 6.5% were above 50 years of age. This implied that majority of the respondents were young adults who are often have vibrant interest in career development for their future lives.

The findings also showed that majority (66.5%) of the respondents were of A-level students which was the focus of the study. A-level students were considered because they at a critical stage of career determination as they prepare to tertiary education. Data in Table 1.2 further indicated that 16.2% of the respondents had degrees and 10.8% had diplomas. These were mainly the teachers of games and sports who were also considered vital in provision of data for this study. At least 6.5% of the respondents had masters degrees. These too were teachers that participated in the study. This implies that all the respondents who participated in this study had an appropriate level of education to have a clear understanding of the items in the self-administered questionnaire. Thus, it is presumed that the data they provided can be reliable in making precise conclusions about the study.

Data presented in Table 1.2 also revealed that 66.5% of the respondents were students who formed the biggest proportion of the unit of analysis. Another 22.7% were classroom teachers who also doubled as games/sports teachers and were therefore, another important category in the unit of analysis. At least 6.5% and 4.3% were the deputy headteachers and headteachers respectively. The proportions of the respondents by designation reflects the representativeness of the respondents in the population of study and therefore, the results of the study may be generalized to the entire target population of study in Sebei sub-region.

Influence of Integration of Students' Needs on Dual Career Development

Table 1.3 presents the descriptive statistics on integration of students' needs with career among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.3: Integration of Students Needs with Careers

Integration of Students' Needs with Career	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
Teachers in this school endeavour to help students in aligning needs training for their career development	0.5	5.4	80.5	13.5	3.07	.455
Aligning students aspirations training with their career needs has helped many of them to develop lifetime careers	0.5	13.0	69.7	16.8	3.03	.566
The teachers have endeavoured to mentor students in integrating career needs with career development	0.0	2.7	62.7	34.6	3.32	.522

The teachers are involved in guiding students in integrating career needs with career development	0.0	1.6	66.5	31.9	3.30	.495
The teachers are also engaged in counselling students in integrating career needs with career development	1.1	0.5	62.7	35.7	3.33	.546
The teachers also support the idea of student coaching by supervisor in order to help them integrate career needs with career development	0.5	20.0	40.5	38.9	3.18	.763
Overall Mean					3.21	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0-1.0 = Integration of students' need with career rarely done; 1.1-2.0 = Integration of students' need with career fairly done; 2.1-3.0 = Integration of students' need with career moderately done; 3.1-4.0 = Integration of students' need with career well done

Data in Table 1.3 showed that majority (80.5%) of the respondent teachers acknowledged that the teachers in the schools endeavoured to help students in aligning needs training for their career development. Only a small proportion of 19.5% disagreed that the teachers in schools endeavoured to help students in aligning needs training for their career development. Similarly, 69.7% of the teachers agreed and 16.8% of them strongly agreed that aligning students aspirations in training with their career needs had helped many of them to develop lifetime careers. A very small proportion of the respondent teachers disagreed in this respect.

Furthermore, the data in Table 1.3 revealed that 62.7% of the respondent teachers agreed and 34.6% of them strongly agreed that they had endeavoured to mentor students in integrating career needs with career development. The data further showed that 66.5% acknowledged that the teachers were involved in guiding students in integrating career needs with career development. Another 62.7% agreed that the teachers were also engaged in counselling students in integrating career needs with career development. Finally, 40.5% agreed while 38.9% of them strongly agreed that the teachers also supported the idea of student coaching by supervisors in order to help them integrate career needs with career development. The overall mean with regard to integration of students' needs with careers was 3.21 implying that integration of students' need with career in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region was well done.

Descriptive Statistics on Development of Academic Careers

Table 1.4 presents descriptive statistics on development of academic careers.

Table 1.4: Development of Academic Careers

Items on Development of Academic Careers	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
Most of the students who have passed through this school have ended up as school teachers	15.7	18.9	24.9	40.5	2.90	1.104
The school has produced several medical doctors since its inception	25.9	7.6	41.1	25.4	2.66	1.122
Most of the students aspire to become lawyers	13.0	25.4	49.7	11.9	2.61	.860
Majority of the students in this school would want to be social workers to serve their communities	1.1	33.0	36.8	29.2	2.94	.815
The school has produced a number of people now working as Public Administrators such as Chief Administrative Officers	25.4	50.3	9.7	14.6	2.14	.960
The students in this school aspire to become Engineers of different categories in their future lifetime	0.0	16.8	63.8	19.5	3.03	.603
Students would like to end up as Statisticians working with different organizations dealing with statistics	2.2	35.1	49.7	13.0	2.74	.707
Overall Mean					2.72	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Academic careers not prioritized; 1.1 - 2.0 = Academic careers fairly prioritized;

2.1 - 3.0 = Academic careers moderately prioritized; 3.1-4.0 = Academic careers well prioritized

Data in Table 1.4 revealed that 24.9% and 40.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the students who had passed through the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had ended up as school teachers. However, 18.9% and 15.7% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that most of the students who had passed through the secondary schools had ended up as school teachers. This implied that not all the students who had studied in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had become teachers. The findings further revealed that 41.1% and 25.4% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the schools had produced several medical doctors since their inception. However, 25.9% and 7.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively that the schools had produced several medical doctors since their inception. This too, implied that the schools had not produced several medical doctors, perhaps some few but not several.

Furthermore, the findings showed that 49.7% and 11.9% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the students from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region aspired to become lawyers. Similarly, 36.8% and 29.2% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that majority of the students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region would want to be social workers to serve their communities. However, 50.3% and 25.4% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the secondary schools had produced a number of people now working in the public sector as Public Administrators such as Chief Administrative Officers. This implied that perhaps on few of the students from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had ended up as Public Administrators.

The findings also showed that majority (63.8%) and 19.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the students in the secondary schools aspired to become Engineers of different categories in their future lifetime. Similarly, majority (49.7% and 13.0% agreed and strongly agreed respectively that students studying in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region would like to end up as Statisticians working with different organizations dealing with statistics. The overall mean for all the items on development of academic careers was 2.72 which according to the legend implied that Academic careers moderately prioritized by students in the secondary schools for their future life.

Before, considering the influence of integration of students' needs on development of academic careers among the students, it was prudent to ascertain their relatedness. Therefore, the results in Table 1.5 show the relatedness of the integration of students' needs to development of academic careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.5: Relatedness of Integration of Students' Needs to Academic Careers Development among students in Secondary Schools in Sebei sub-region

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.637	.271		-2.354	.020
	Integration of Students' Needs with Career	1.099	.082	.703	13.388	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Academic career development

The results in Table 1.5 indicated a significance value (Sig) of .000 implying that integration of students' needs is significantly related to academic careers development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Regression Analysis

Table 1.6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.703 ^a	.495	.492	.787

a. Predictors: (Constant), Integration of Students' Needs with Career

The R square value was .495 which can be converted to percent (.495 x 100) giving 49.5%. This means that for every unit change in supporting students in integration of their needs with careers in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, academic careers development improves by 49.5%. To determine whether or not such a change causes a significant influence, the ANOVA results in Table 1.7 were considered.

Table 1.7: Influence of Support in Integration of Students' Needs with Careers on Academic careers Development among Students in Sec. Schools in Sebei Sub-Region (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	110.961	1	110.961	179.242	.000 ^b
	Residual	113.288	183	.619		
	Total	224.249	184			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic career development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Integration of Students' Needs with Career

The significance (Sig) value was found to be .000 which was less than 0.05 (the standard). This implies that there is a strong significant influence of supporting integration of students' needs with careers on academic careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Integration of Students' Needs and Sports Careers Development

Having considered the influence of integration of students' needs with career on academic careers development among students, it was prudent to now consider influence on sports careers development.

Descriptive Statistics on Development of Sports Careers

Table 1.8 presents the descriptive statistics on development of sports careers.

Table 1.8: Descriptive Statistics on Development of Sports Careers

Items on Development of Sports Careers	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
There are students who would like to work as Sports Directors in future.	1.6	18.4	51.4	28.6	3.07	.730
Some of the students who completed from this school now work as Sports Managers	15.1	36.2	47.0	1.6	2.35	.752
A number of the students are now working as Directors in the sports field around the country	19.5	51.9	25.9	2.7	2.12	.742
Majority of our students are now Trainers in various sporting activities	2.2	25.9	69.7	2.2	2.72	.539
We have several of our former students who are Referees in the sports field	2.2	19.5	64.9	13.5	2.90	.639
Some of our students would want to work as Umpires for some of the common sports activities in the country	0.5	19.5	51.4	28.6	3.08	.706
Overall Mean					2.71	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Sports careers not prioritized; 1.1 - 2.0 = Sports careers fairly prioritized;

2.1 - 3.0 = Sports careers moderately prioritized; 3.1-4.0 = Sports careers well prioritized

Data in Table 1.8 showed that majority (51.4%) of the respondents agreed and another 28.6% of them strongly agreed that there were students who liked to work as sports directors in future. However, a small proportion of 18.4% disagreed and 1.6% strongly disagreed that there were students who liked to work as sports directors in future. This implied that there were a significant number of students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region who had interest in development of a sports career. The results further showed that 47.0% of the respondents acknowledged that some of the students who completed from the secondary school in Sebei sub-region now work as sports managers. However, another 36.2% disagreed in this regard. This implies that while some of the students who completed from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were already working as sports managers, the others were not. Perhaps they were engaged in other careers.

Furthermore, the results in Table 1.8 revealed that majority (51.9%) of the respondents disagreed with another 19.5% of them strongly disagreeing that a number of the students were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. At least 25.9% and 2.7% of them agreed and strongly agreed respectively that a number of the students were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. This implies that some few of the students who studied in the

secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. The results also indicated that majority (69.7%) of the respondents acknowledged that most of the students were now trainers in various sporting activities. Similarly, majority (64.9%) of the respondents agreed and 13.5% of them strongly agreed that they had several of their former students who were referees in the sports field. Another 51.4% agreed and 28.6% strongly agreed that some of their students would want to work as umpires for some of the common sports activities in the country. The overall mean for all the items on development of the sports careers was 2.71 which according to the legend also implied that sports careers moderately prioritized by many students who aspired to take on sports careers for their future life. Table 1.9 shows the relatedness of the development of career opportunities to development of sports careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

The transformed means from the results in Table 1.3 (for integration of students' needs) and that in Table 1.8 (for sports careers development) were used to first ascertain the relatedness and then secondly run the linear regression. Table 1.9 presents the results for the relatedness of integration of students' needs and sports careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.9: Relatedness of Integration of Students' Needs to Sports of Sports Careers Development in Secondary Schools in Sebei sub-region

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.751	.197		-3.813	.000
1 Integration of Students' Needs with Career	1.151	.060	.819	19.279	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sports career development

The significance value (Sig) of .000 implying that integration of students' needs is significantly related to sports career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Regression Analysis for Influence of Integration of Students' Needs on sports Career Development among Students

In order to determine the influence of integration of students' needs with career on the sports career development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, a linear regression was run using the transformed overall means in Table 1.3 (i.e 3.07) for integration of students' needs and that in Table 1.8 (i.e. 2.71) for sports career development. The results of the linear regression are presented in Table 1.10 and Table 1.11.

Table 1.10: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.819 ^a	.670	.668	.572

a. Predictors: (Constant), Integration of Students' Needs with Career

The R square value was .670 which can be converted to percent (.670 x 100) giving 67.0%. This means that for every unit change in supporting students in integration of students' career needs in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, sports career development improves by 67.2%. To determine whether or not such a change causes a significant influence, the ANOVA results in Table 1.11 were considered.

Table 1.11: Influence of Integration of Students' Needs with Career on Sports Career Development among Students in Sec. Schools in Sebei (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	121.722	1	121.722	371.676	.000 ^b
	Residual	59.932	183	.327		
	Total	181.654	184			

a. Dependent Variable: Sports career development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Integration of Students' Needs with Career

The significance (Sig) value was found to be .000 which was less than 0.05 (the standard). This implies that there is a very strong significant influence of supporting integration of students' needs with career on sports career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

The quantitative results for development of both academic and sports careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were closely in agreement with the qualitative data gathered through face-to-face interviews with several participants. For instance, in a face-to-face interview with one of the deputy headteachers of the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region (R-DHT-01) said:

"Integrating helps or enables the learners to achieve in both fields co-currently with proper monitoring. The learner may find it hard to perform both careers to the expectation. Integration of career opportunities can strain the learners or students in achieving both careers. There is high cost in managing both careers both financially and time."

Regarding the issue of whether monitoring is done in the schools, one of the directors of studies (R-DOS-05) acknowledged and said:

"Yes the monitoring is done both but majorly in the academics and a few talented student athletes are monitored closely."

Similarly, another respondent director of studies (R-DOS-03) also acknowledged that monitoring is done by the teachers. He said:

"Yes, monitoring is done. The teachers identify learners with different career abilities and for those who are good at the games and sports, the responsible teachers will guide them in building their sports career alongside the academics. Monitoring is also done through inter class or inter house termly school competitions where learners of a particular career are grouped and guided accordingly. In the same vein learners who excel in both sports and academics are pruned accordingly."

However, some participants had different views with regard to integration and monitoring of career development among the students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. For instance, in a face-to-face interview with one director of studies (R-DOS-07) he said:

"Integration is in most cases not being done but if given time it can impact positively on the learners' career development since they can be able to identify what they can do best. This can be greatly realized if both the teachers and the learners are well motivated. If the teachers can do their part to the expected standard, and also use the role models like Joshua Cheptegie, Stephen Kiprotich, they would boost the students' morale. The students would definitely engage in dual career development."

Furthermore, the qualitative data revealed that integration of students' career needs had a lot of benefits. For instance, one director of studies (R-DOS-08) said:

"It enables learners to earn a living even without attaining any equalization of without finishing S4. A case in point is some students who during their time can waste as boda boda riders, house helps, work in garages and earn a living. Alongside teaching, learners get the skills of sporting activities like athletics, football basketball among others. Some like Joshua Cheptegie who while at school, he was training as an athletic yet he did not compromise his studios. It's through this that he has potentially used his talent."

Similarly, the respondent deputy headteachers also acknowledged the benefits of integration of students career needs. One deputy headteacher (R-DHT-06) said:

"A learner is able to choose his/her area of specialization for example football alongside education. It does so by reducing frustration. If a learner fails in one field, then he/she can succeed in the other."

Furthermore, as far as influence of integration of students' needs on dual career development was concerned, one director of studies (R-DOS-03) said:

"It enables learners to make right choices from an informed point of view. This later on encourages specialization."

Divergent views were noted when some respondents indicated that challenges were experienced in integration of career information with students needs. One sports officer (R-SO-02) said:

“Little emphasis has always been put in sports but more in academics. Career guidance sessions themselves are not so much upheld since most private schools are result oriented.”

Yet another sports officer (R-SO-01) said:

“As learners understand their career needs it becomes easier for them to ingrates so on identifying them strength in the of the talent that they possess alongside their academic abilities. When properly understood it boosts their dual career development positively.”

Similarly, one director of studies (R-DOS-05) explained and said:

“When well integrated in the school setting, they can be seen as role models to other. These below then can be motivated to follow what their friend is doing. When well integrated, their families can help to uplift their family backgrounds especially those who are studying and participating in athletics. In addition that who is handling both have more opportunities compared to that one doing only sports. Specialization is encouraged. After graduation, such learners are always given time to deviant to only what he can do best. It he sees that he can no longer perform well in athletics or sports time to join his profession. This reduces frustration.”

From the above quotations, it was evident that integration of students' needs was not a straight forward issue and presented with challenges. Nevertheless, some scholars (Surujal, 2016; Guidotti et al, 2014; Izzicupo et al, 2021) integration can significantly enhance career development only if those involved in the integration process understand how to execute it. This implies that not all people or teachers can undertake integration of individual students' needs in a school setting. The pertinent question than would be, how suited are the teachers in the secondary school when it comes to integration of students' needs. This perhaps explains why whereas teachers in the secondary schools have attempted to carry out integration of students' needs, it has not significantly enhanced career development among the students.

Both quantitative and qualitative data collected closely corroborated with the findings of other studies elsewhere. It has been noted that currently, elite sport is undergoing an important professionalization process, which means that athletes spend a large part of their time training and competing (Vilanova & Puig, 2013). In this sense, Wylleman et al. (2013) explain that the development of a high-level sports career requires an enormous dedication in the years before it, in which the athlete acquires the skills and experience necessary to be able to compete at the highest level and turn this sports practice into a profession. However, as in all professional fields, it is clear that there is a day when this sports career ends. Because these careers end prematurely compared to other professional careers, Mateu et al. (2018) emphasize that some of these elite athletes who finish their sports careers must live from another professional activity. In line with this, some studies, such as that of Aquilina (2013) and Puig and Vilanova (2006), shows that an adequate balance of the sports career and academic life allows athletes to face the transition process more efficiently. This conciliation also enables the preparation of an alternative working life outside the sports world after the sport's retirement. As a result of this combination of careers, the concept of dual career was born, which was the subject of this study.

The findings of the study showed that majority of the respondents acknowledged that teachers were engaged in the integration of students' needs with career among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. For instance, the findings indicated that integration of students' needs was significantly related to academic careers development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. In terms of magnitude, findings indicated that for every unit effort in supporting students in integration of their needs with careers in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, academic careers development improved by 49.5%. This implied that there was a strong significant influence of supporting integration of students' needs with careers on academic careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

With regard to sporting careers, the study findings revealed that integration of students' needs with career was also significantly related to sports career development among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. In terms of magnitude, the findings revealed that for every unit effort in supporting students in integration of career needs with careers in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, sports career development improved by 67.2%. Therefore, there was

a very strong significant influence of supporting integration of students' needs with career on sports career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

5. CONCLUSIONS

From the findings of the study and the discussion therefrom, the study concluded that there was a strong significant influence of supporting integration of students' needs with careers on academic careers development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. There was a very strong significant influence of supporting integration of students' needs with career on sports career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. However, Influence on sports career development was one and a half times higher than for academic career development. Therefore, out of every ten (10) students supported in integration of their career need with available careers, six (6) would choose to engage in a sports career development while only four (4) would choose to engage in an academic career development.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Career teachers need to provide guidance tailored to the needs of each student to allow for integration of student needs with career opportunities. Mass guidance to groups of students does not provide for integration of individual needs.
- ii. Career teachers should endeavour to programme the guidance process so as to interact with individual students to provide for appropriate integration of students needs with career opportunities.

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